

GENERAL ISSUES IN CORPORA DATA ANALYSIS

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1 INTRODUCTION

Once the data is ready, we can then start the linguistic investigations. Some common approach categorizations are bottom-up and top-down approaches (Biber 2007); corpus-driven and corpus-based approaches (see, e.g., Biber 2015: 193–224); exploratory and focused approaches (see Partington 2009; Gries 2010; Gabrielatos 2018); and deductive and inductive approaches (Stefanowitsch 2020).

These categorizations, with some differences, distinguish two main approaches. In the exploratory approach, the research starts with a very general question, with an open-mind approach to the data (Stefanowitsch 2020:61). This approach can raise specific hypotheses which can then be investigated with the focused approach. When conducting a focused investigation, the observations about the data are restricted to the elements in question.

2 TOOLS FOR CORPUS ANALYSIS

The choice of tools for data analysis varies according to the research question(s); the language used; the type of analysis; personal interest; the type of data annotation, etc. Usually, web applications like SketchEngine (Kilgarriff et al. 2014) or standalone tools like AntConc (Anthony 2022) are preferred among researchers with no programming skills, for their usability.

However, it has some drawbacks, such as the limited number of functionalities. For users looking for customization, the use of programming language libraries is preferred. A downside of this method is the steep learning curve. Normally, the more sophisticated or powerful the tool is, the more it will allow the user to better explore the potential of the data.

3 SEARCHES

3.1 TYPES OF QUERIES

Corpora can be queried by the orthographic word(s) and its variation; by the relationship of these tokens to other tokens (context); or by a combination of these two. In many cases, orthographic searches (or word form searches) are sufficient. Also, most corpus search systems allow for the use of regular expressions, which allows for searches by patterns. However, to search for advanced combinations of tokens and their annotations, we need a robust query system. These systems allow us to look for (sequences of) tokens and their annotations. Some examples are the Corpus Query Processor (CQP) (Evert 2008), the Corpus Query Language (CQL) (Jakubíček et al. 2010), and ANNIS (Zeldes et al. 2009).

3.2 PRECISION AND RECALL

For as powerful a query processor can be or for as good as a query can be written, it is very unlikely the search result is a perfect representation of what we intended. We have to consider that among the results we can have true positives (what we expected) and false positives (not what we expected). We should also consider that search might fail to identify some expected results (false negative) and unexpected results (true negative). With these results, we can calculate the precision (ratio of relevant retrieved items and all retrieved items) and the recall (ratio of retrieved relevant items over all relevant items) of the results.

4 FREQUENCY

4.1 SIGNIFICANCE TESTING AND EFFECT-SIZE

Frequency is the core of quantitative studies, but frequency on its own can be deceiving and unreliable, as it only gives information about the sample our data is aiming to represent. For this reason, we should use statistical significance tests to verify whether our result was not obtained by chance, but that it “reflects the characteristics of the population from which the sample was drawn” (Sirking 2006: 306). We can also use effect-size measures to get the strength of the difference or relationship found in our results (see, e.g., Ellis 2010: 3-5; Gabrielatos 2018).

4.2 DISPERSION

Besides the aforementioned tests, another important piece of information is to know how the observed pattern is distributed across corpus units. This is normally acquired by applying dispersion measures. Dispersion may be defined as the degree to which occurrences of a word (or lemmas, phrases, annotations of any sort) are distributed through a corpus uniformly. If a word occurs much more often in one text of a corpus than in the other texts, it can be said to be unevenly dispersed. Conversely, an evenly dispersed word is expected to have a relatively constant presence across all corpus texts (Gries 2008). There are different methods and measures to calculate dispersion (see e.g., Gries 2020). A very simplistic, yet widely used way of reporting the distribution of frequencies in a corpus is range, as it takes only a simple count of how many texts or sections in the corpus feature the searched word.

5 COOCCURRENCES AND RELATIONSHIPS

Investigating the relationship between elements (tokens, annotation) in texts is a very common practice when analysing corpora. A straightforward method is the generation of frequency lists of n-grams. N-grams are sequences of a given number of words. They are widely used in language modelling (see, e.g., Jurafsky & Martin 2021). In research focused on the discourse, these sequences are also known as lexical bundles (Biber et al. 1999).

A commonly used technique to investigate cooccurrences for specific words is the exploration of collocations, or “the phenomenon surrounding the fact that certain words are more likely to occur in combination with other words in certain contexts” (Baker et al. 2006:36). The method used to identify collocations impact greatly on the results and the choice for the most suitable measure varies according to the intent of the research (see, e.g., Evert 2009).

When we want to have a general understanding of the main ideas in a corpus, clustering and topic modelling are frequently used techniques of data exploration. Clustering involves grouping the tokens in the corpus into meaningful groups. Two common clustering methods are the scatter browsing method and the hierarchical clustering. The scatter method is more suitable for an exploratory approach (see e.g., Cutting et al. 1992; Hearst and Pedersen 1996), while the hierarchical allows for query-specific investigations (Feldman & Sanger, 2006:82-84).

Topic modelling is a specific type of clustering often used for text analysis, especially to aid researchers to summarize and explore large corpora. The cooccurrence works on a document level rather than by segment span. “Topic modeling algorithms (...) analyze the words of the original texts to discover the themes that run through them [and] how those themes are

connected to each other” (Blei 2012:7), and Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) (Blei et. al, 2003) is probably the most used model.

6 CONTRASTING

A common way of investigating the difference between two datasets is through the calculation of keyness, or distinctiveness. By calculating keyness we can identify keywords, items that occur in a corpus or corpus section more often than would be expected. For a better understanding of the different measures to calculate distinctiveness and their implications, see Du et al. (2021).

Data analysis is very often an incremental cycle. Refined hypotheses are derived from previous research. For this, and many other reasons, when performing data investigations, it is crucial to document and share data and procedures taken to achieve the final results.

7 REFERENCES

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